

Efficient Planning and Execution of Solar Panels using BIM 4D with Line of Balance schedule

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Abstract

Traditionally, the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) sector has been heavily dependent on non-renewable energy resources, resulting in significant environmental degradation and long-term risks. However, solar panels offer a promising alternative that can address these sustainability challenges. This study explores how the integration of solar panels, Building Information Modelling (BIM), and adherence to lean principles can enhance sustainability and improve efficiency within AEC projects.

Transitioning to renewable energy sources, such as solar panels, fosters a reduction in carbon footprint and operational costs while reducing greenhouse gas emissions. By incorporating BIM and Lean Principles into sustainable practices, collaboration is enhanced, efficiency is optimised, and waste generated during construction is minimised.

This dissertation focuses on how the BIM 4D methodology can achieve optimal sequencing and simulation in a solar panel project. By exploring challenges and ideal methodologies associated with BIM software for project planning and scheduling, this research seeks to

underscore how adopting a 4D model can enhance competencies and lead to significant gains in executing infrastructure projects.

It is intended to benchmark these concepts within some pilot testing using available software tools in the market, such as Prevision, MS Project, Navisworks, Bexel Manager, Synchro, VisiLean, and Augin, towards proficient digital construction and planning. Methods like Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) and Macro-flow analysis will be applied alongside them to create animated representations.

The study follows a structured case approach: an introduction, literature review, 4D BIM Modelling, case study, application, and conclusions. The dissertation proposes utilising BIM 4D modelling on a solar panel construction site. The case study is in Ossendrecht, Netherlands, with 27,275.700 kWp energy production and 90.126 photovoltaic solar panels to be delivered in 10 months.

The main execution contractor is a high-innovation construction company from Germany, referred in this dissertation as Company A. Specialising in the turnkey construction of commercial, industrial, and large-scale solar installations, Company A has 20 years of experience and a vision of clean energy worldwide. On the other hand, company B is a start-up in Brazil that specialises in lean construction. It helps companies achieve their results, explores the benefits of applying a Line of Balance, and assists in boosting the time project deliverable, reducing costs, and analysing waste.

This study will aim to engage stakeholders in using these techniques and provide insights into their practical application and impact on project management practices. It may be helpful as an example for other companies and projects that are trying to contribute to leveraging BIM 4D and increasing digital maturity in this kind of project.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

https://youtu.be/_wG_S1B5Vbw

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